

PRINCIPLES AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE ORGANIZATION OF MANAGEMENT ACTIVITIES (ON THE EXAMPLE OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION)

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Annotation: The article tells about the work carried out in the shadow of preschool education, about the decisions and their implementation made by our president and the Ministry of Preschool Education, about current innovations and achievements and shortcomings in the field of education, about what aspects should be paid attention to for the formation of healthy competition, the development of the taste sphere of preschool education, training, the use of new pedagogical technologies, innovations in the nutrition system.

Keywords: Preschool education, qualitative changes, socio-economic relations, skills and competencies.

ПРИНЦИПЫ И МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ)

Аннотация: В статье рассказывается о работе, проводимой в тени дошкольного образования, о решениях и их реализации, принятых нашим президентом и Министерством дошкольного образования, о текущих инновациях и достижениях и недостатках в сфере образования, о том, на какие аспекты следует обратить внимание для формирования здоровой конкуренции, развитие вкусовой сферы дошкольного образования, тренингов, использование новых педагогических технологий, инноваций в системе питания.

Ключевые слова: Дошкольное образование, качественные изменения, социально-экономические отношения, навыки и компетенции.

BOSHQARUV FAOLIYATINI TASHKIL ETISH TAMOYILLARI VA USLUBIY ASOSLARI (MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM MISOLIDA)

Annotatsiya: maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim soyasida olib borilayotgan ishlar, Prezidentimiz va maktabgacha ta'lim vazirligi tomonidan qabul qilingan qarorlar va ularni amalga oshirish, ta'lim sohasidagi joriy innovatsiyalar, yutuqlar va kamchiliklar, sog'lom ta'lim uchun qanday jihatlarga e'tibor qaratish kerakligi haqida so'z boradi. raqobat, maktabgacha ta'limning did sohasini rivojlantirish, ta'lim, yangi pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish, oziq-ovqat tizimidagi innovatsiyalar.

Kalit so'zlar: erta bolalik ta'limi, sifatli o'zgarishlar, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy munosabatlar, ko'nikma va malakalar.

INTRODUCTION

The reforms and changes taking place today in the field of education, day by day show their effectiveness in improving the quality of education and achieving high results.

In particular, the work carried out in the field of preschool education is of great importance for expanding the horizons of the younger generation, in order to grow up in the future as mature people, selfless people of their profession, based on their own capabilities, abilities and talents.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Whatever industry we take, we will not be able to achieve any changes, a prosperous life without the education of modern mature personnel. The training of such personnel, a healthy gene pool of the nation, begins, first of all, with the preschool education system.

Comparing a child who was educated in kindergarten with a child who did not attend kindergarten, it is not difficult to notice that there is a difference between their level of thinking between the Earth and the sky.

That is why we have raised the issue of revising the preschool education system to the level of state policy and have started a lot of work in this direction. If we do not implement this decision comprehensively, it will be difficult for us to achieve qualitative changes in the entire education system, to ensure the continuity of education," President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said.

In his book "Let's build our great future together with our brave and noble people" Mirziyoyev admits that "a devoted to his people, capable of continuing what we have begun, a comprehensively mature leader faces an urgent task – to educate the next generation in a perfect person."

In the development of socio-economic relations in the XXI century, it is becoming obvious every day that human intelligence and intelligence, spirituality are the main coordinating, developing factors and tools.

The quality of education in the pre-school education system is determined by the upbringing and professional development of personnel, determined by the abilities and labor activity of a specialist who successfully carries out professional activities in accordance with the requirements and proposals of economic development at the present stage of the education system.

Preschool educational institutions develop educational activities, the quality of education determines the quality of the educational result not so much in connection with the planning, implementation of the educational process, curriculum, curricula, as in connection with the quality of education and knowledge, skills and abilities independently acquired by pupils.

The revision of the preschool education system in Uzbekistan consists in paying attention to the quality of the educational process during the radical reform, organizing it taking into account the most favorable and effective aspects, directing the reforms to personal improvement, developing a broad outlook among pupils, as well as instilling in society a propensity for necessary activities.

The new preschool education program, introduced in September 2018, has been brought to all preschool institutions in accordance with the requirements of the state. However, all preschool institutions are also provided with thematic planning programs.

A program called "The first step" has not lost its value to this day, and quite fruitful work on this program is being carried out to this day.

Minister of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan Agrippina Shin commented: "In general, the state requirements state that the development of children of primary and preschool age should be carried out in five directions. By developing these five areas, the child acquires 4 competencies, that is, he becomes motivated to enter the 1st grade."

RESULTS

The new programs focus on the child and his interests. The teacher forms a unified social environment with such social partners as the parent, the teaching staff, as well as the child himself, society and the state.

According to Resolution No. PD 3651, for the first time in Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Preschool Education has developed rules for public-private partnership (PPP). This rule specifies 10 PPP models to which entrepreneurs are involved. Benefits and preferences have been established for these entrepreneurs.

A lot of work is being done on the introduction of such competitions as the Best educator, the best head on the issues of financial incentives for preschool education in the preschool education system, on the problems of the nutrition system, on the training and retraining of personnel, to ensure the coverage of preschool children with equal and high-quality education.

Currently, a state program has been adopted to expand the network of preschool educational institutions, strengthen their material and technical base, and build new preschool institutions. Based on the experience of developed countries, we can say that the creation of a non-governmental educational institution creates the basis for the formation of healthy competition.

Much attention is paid to the training of specialized personnel in the field of preschool education. The decisions taken and implemented today are aimed at strengthening the education and upbringing of the younger generation, expanding its knowledge, worldview, and the formation of necessary life skills.

DISCUSSION

The development of new pedagogical technologies, methods and techniques that meet modern requirements in the field of preschool education, as well as the creation of new literature and manuals is one of the most important tasks of our time.

Much attention is paid to the organization of qualified medical care, the organization of a nutrition system at the level of established norms that meet sanitary and hygienic standards, professional development of a medical worker, provision of information and communication technologies, critical consideration of cases of their connection to the Internet, provision of fiction and educational literature intended for preschool educational institutions.

The issue of forming a new generation of preschool education system managers is also among the topical issues of everyday life. At the same time, the recognized functions of the head, which must be performed in harmony with the tasks of coordination, planning, regulation, control and evaluation, lead to the intellectual maturation of children, the formation of a spiritually harmonious personality and scientific and spiritual growth of teaching staff, strengthening of political and civic position.

CONCLUSIONS

In connection with the implementation of a number of reforms in the field of preschool education in the republic, the scientific and pedagogical staff has changed in almost all preschool institutions of the country, modern curricula have been developed, the material and technical base has been updated, the pedagogical and psychological foundations of the functioning of the preschool education system have been laid, the emergence of healthy competition between state and non-state preschool educational institutions, legal and regulatory fundamentals of educational activity., the use of world experience in the management system, their application in the educational process, intensive work is being carried out on the study and use of new pedagogical technologies, the definition and practical application of measures based on them.

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